

Use images for free and royalty-free

Version: V1

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Date: 11.02.2025

Citation: Röhrig, B. (2025). Use images for free and royalty-free. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851966>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14851966

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Aim of the article

The article presents ways of using free and royalty-free images and what should be considered when using them. The images and other media such as photos, pictures, images, illustrations, graphics, videos, sounds, etc. can be used in scientific presentations, lectures and articles, as well as in the private and business sector.

Free use of images

Images, pictures, photos and graphics enhance a text, a presentation or a brochure. In general, the use of suitable images in publications, lectures and other representations makes sense, both in the official and private spheres. In the following, possibilities are presented to use images free of charge with or without citing the source.

Various platforms are recommended on the basis of our own research:

1. Pixabay GmbH: <https://pixabay.com>
2. Pexels GmbH: <https://www.pexels.com>
3. FLATICON <https://www.flaticon.com>
4. Openverse: <https://openverse.org>
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6. Unsplash <https://unsplash.com>

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Background: Copyright

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Further links

Wikipedia: <https://www.wikipedia.org>

The free internet encyclopaedia Wikipedia is another good way to access free images. Images posted on Wikipedia can be downloaded and used free of charge, the source must be indicated. The link is provided next to the download of the images.

Commercial portals

In addition to the possibility of using images free of charge, there are countless commercial portals where fees are charged for the use of the images. This ranges from paying for individual images to 'group cards' for multiple images to subscriptions over a certain period of time, such as months or years. The best-known portals are: iStock, Adobe Stock, Shutterstock and others.

Good luck with using the various photos, images and graphics, in the scientific, private or official sector!